

DEVELOPMENT OF A KNITTED FABRIC REINFORCED ELASTOMERIC COMPOSITE INTERVERTEBRAL DISC PROSTHESIS

S. Ramakrishna¹, S. Ramaswamy¹, S. H. Teoh² and C. T. Tan³

¹ *Centre for Biomedical Materials Applications and Technology (BIOMAT),
Department of Mechanical and Production Engineering, National University of Singapore,
10 Kent Ridge Crescent, Singapore 119260.*

² *Institute of Materials Research and Engineering (IMRE), National University of Singapore,
10 Kent Ridge Crescent, Singapore 119260.*

³ *Department of Orthopaedic Surgery, Singapore General Hospital
Outram Road, Singapore 169608*

SUMMARY: The concept of an intervertebral disc prosthesis (IVDP) has arisen from the limited success of current surgical measures to treat disc degeneration. In this study, a textile composite IVDP with a polymeric core was successfully fabricated. Issues relating to the design and process optimisation of the IVDP fabrication are discussed. In addition, the mechanical behaviour of the IVDP are compared with the mechanical behaviour of the natural intervertebral disc (IVD).

KEYWORDS: intervertebral disc prosthesis, rotational moulding, textile composites, elastomers

INTRODUCTION

In spite of their limited application thus far in the area of biomaterials, textile composites offer the potential to better match the mechanical properties of hard tissue and improve overall device performance [1]. This is due to the fact that most living tissues are three-dimensional fibrous collagen structures. In this regard, the human IVD [Fig. 1] is no exception since it comprises of fibrous composite (annular) layers that surround a gel like liquid core [2].

From a viewpoint of the mechanical requirements, an IVDP must primarily possess similar modulus and deformation properties to the natural IVD. Conventional materials cannot be exclusively considered since they cannot match the mechanical properties. For example, elastomeric polymers offer flexibility but are insufficient in modulus and tear strength. Thus, the immediate objective in this study was to apply textile composites concepts to the fabrication of an IVDP in an attempt to match the primary mechanical properties of the IVD. Two key areas are reported in this paper. These are: 1] design and process optimisation and 2] the compressive behaviour of the IVDPs.

IVDP DESIGNS

Liquid-Filled IVDP

An excised human cadaveric disc was used as the basis to fabricate open IVDP moulds. Subsequently, permanent aluminium open moulds were made [Figure 2]. Permanent aluminium closed moulds were then fabricated with a 3 mm reduction in all directions, in order to accommodate for a core polymeric region as well a composite layer to encapsulate the former.

Rotational Moulding

The natural IVD is a hollow, liquid-filled entity and to replicate this, computer controlled liquid rotational moulding (CCLRM) a method known for the making of hollow products was incorporated. CCLRM was carried out using a Kent Ridge Instruments, version RM100 workstation [Fig. 3] which also allows for environmental control of temperature and humidity [3]. The use of the computer to control bi-axial speeds allowed for greater precision in obtaining greater uniformity in thickness distribution. Optimum speed profiles for CCLRM were constructed from conducting flow visualisation studies. CCLRM requires the use of a mouldable liquid and a polyurethane elastomer (thermoset) (monothane Grade A60, Compounding Ingredients Limited (CIL), Lancashire, UK) was used because of its practicality in studying the fabrication process. The closed CCLRM of the monothane was used to make the hollow IVDP.

Figure 1: Intervertebral disc structure

Figure 2: Open Mould of Intervertebral Disc Prosthesis

Figure 3: Computer Controlled Liquid Rotational Moulding (CCLRM) Machine

Optimisation of Rotational Moulding

CCLRM brings with it several variables related to the mould or processing that have to be addressed in order to consistently obtain an acceptable product. Mould variables include mouldable material properties, mould quality and amount of mouldable material used. With respect to the processing variables, temperature/humidity and speeds/speed ratio have to be studied. The material to be moulded had to be liquid in nature and also have sufficient curing time to allow for adequate and complete coating of the mould interior. Monothane was found to be suited for this purpose. Furthermore, because it reached its lowest viscosity point prior to

its actual curing temperature, it went through a natural degassing stage which would prevent bubble entrapment. The permanent aluminium closed moulds allowed for a smooth and permanent surface for the moulding material to coat over. This would ensure a better moulded product. Based on a number of moulding trials, it was determined that approximately 5.4 to 6 grams of material was the ideal weight for moulding of the hollow IVDP.

It was found that monothane did not reach its minimum viscosity point when the oven temperature display indicated a temperature of 140°C (curing temperature of monothane) for approximately 15 minutes. Since this would mean that it would therefore eventually arrive at its minimum viscosity temperature when the temperature of the oven was still at 140°C, this meant that the oven temperature could be kept constant at 140°C. In order to maintain the humidity, the exhaust fan was used during the moulding cycle to maintain a dryer environmental chamber.

The speeds and speed ratios to be used for moulding is an important parameter to optimise. If the speeds were too slow, then an incomplete moulded product would result since the material would simply form a pool at the bottom of the mould surface. If the speeds were too fast, the thickness distribution of the moulded product would be very uneven and hence undesirable especially where biomaterials are concerned since this could provoke increased thrombus formation. Speed ratio is constant for a particular geometry of mould. Flow visualisation studies were conducted using an external mould with a rod attachment. Using different viscosities of a dyed and diluted fluid (Dow Corning silicone fluid 350cs, USA), the major and minor speeds were varied according to the observed thickness distribution of the liquid on the mould surface. From this, a speed ratio was determined and a speed profile was constructed as described in Fig 4.

Figure 4: Speed Profile for CCLRM

Liquid-Filled Composite IVDP

Samples of liquid-filled IVDPs were inserted into a pocket that had a weft knit structure [Fig.5]. This structure was fabricated using a flat bed knitting machine and was made from aramid (Kevlar, DuPont Ltd., USA) yarns. Kevlar was chosen because of its potential use in implants [4]. The IVDP held in the knitted fabric was then dipped in monothane and was left submerged in the resin at a temperature of 120°C for two hours and then at 140°C for one hour. Subsequently, the whole set-up was placed in a larger disc cavity mould which matched the dimensions of our IVDP design requirement. The hollow composite IVDP was then injected with water.

Solid Composite IVDP

A solid IVDP was also fabricated. This was performed by complete filling of the IVDP mould cavity by liquid monothane and allowing to cure by heating for a period of 8 hours. As before, subsequent application of the composite layer was performed to encapsulate the IVDP.

Figure 5: Weft Knitted Structure

DISCUSSION ON COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR

Natural IVD

Typical stress-strain relationships for the natural IVD are depicted in Fig.6 [5]. The modulus values are seen in Table 1. An upper and lower range define the limits of a normal disc.

Beyond the upper limit, axial stiffness would be too high and below the lower limit would imply a degenerative disc. The modulus was calculated in both an initial (at less than 0.2 KN load) and final region (close to the peak modulus of the curve) (hereby called slope 1 (E_{c1}) and slope 2 (E_{c2}) respectively).

Liquid Filled IVDP

Compression testing of the three different cases of prostheses were performed. These were 1] liquid-filled IVDP, 2] liquid-filled, composite encapsulated IVDP and 3] solid, composite encapsulated IVDP. The compressive behaviour of these IVDPs can be seen in Figure 7. The curves clearly display a bi-modulus stress-strain relationship, hence the rationale for defining an initial and final region. Figure 7 has a defined strain limit of 10 % even though our IVDPs could deform in excess of 100 % when greater loads were applied. The reason for this is that in situ testing has determined surface strains on the IVD to be in the range of about 6 to 10 % for a load of 2150 N [6].

Figure 6: Upper and lower limits of a normal IVD as defined by [5]

Concentrating first on the water-filled nucleus alone, note that the steep region beyond 80% strain is not truly indicative of the sample since it was observed that leakage of the water inside occurred at roughly 10 N of load. When a large part of the water leaked out, the sample would be flattened and as a result, very little deformation could be possible at that point. Although leakage is evidence of nucleus failure, rupture, which is more catastrophic did not occur.

Although testing of the hollow, liquid-filled IVDP was not found to be optimum, it served several other purposes. Namely these were to determine a trend in the stiffness properties, to observe the compressive properties of the nucleus alone which may on its own also serve as a disc replacement and finally also to determine the benefits of a hollow, liquid-filled structure which essentially replicates the form of the IVD.

Liquid-Filled, Composite IVDP

This IVDP displayed consistent moduli values with the two slopes but were found to be lower than desired. This was perhaps due to leakage of liquid which was again observed, but was less extreme. Another related problem was that the adhesive used to seal the site of liquid injection degraded after the heating and this also caused some weakening of the matrix and resin. However, further investigation to a liquid-filled composite IVDP is necessary as the distribution of stress and the method of absorption of loads may be important in ensuring IVDP viability. This view is reinforced because fluid pressurisation is thought to be critical in equipping the means by which the IVD supports load [7].

Solid Composite IVDP

In essence, a solid IVDP without the composite layer is a representation of the compressive behaviour of the volume of monothane in use and it was thus not compared independently.

Table 1: Compressive modulus values of nucleus and IVDP at two distinct slopes

TYPE	MODULUS (KPa) (SLOPE1) [E_{c1}]	MODULUS (KPa) (SLOPE 2) [E_{c2}]
NATURAL IVD (CALCULATED FROM FIGURE 9)	$20.78 < E_{c1} < 103.90$	$74.21 < E_{c2} < 173.16$
SOLID NUCLEUS WITH COMPOSITE LAYER	17.24	40.00
WATER-FILLED NUCLEUS WITH COMPOSITE LAYER	7.41	20.98
WATER-FILLED NUCLEUS	8.36	95.62

Figure 7: Compressive behaviour of IVDPs

However a solid, composite IVDP was fabricated and tested because it may sufficiently provide the required mechanical properties and as a consequence simplify the IVDP process considerably. This would enable a more consistent and desirable product.

From Figure 7, it can be seen that the solid, composite IVDP provides a compressive behaviour that limits the deformation and hence provides a higher stiffness. Secondly being solid, failure by way of leakage or adhesion loss does not occur. It was determined that the compressive modulus of a fibre reinforced solid IVDP design by [5] was 23.6 KPa in slope 1 and 86.6 KPa in slope two. A comparison between our solid IVDP and the fibre reinforced disc described in [5] describes the latter as having higher stiffness. However this is expected because the strain rates in the former are very high due to its elastomeric properties. Nevertheless, the compressive behaviour of the solid IVDP was found to be fairly adequate.

One of the difficulties in assessing optimum IVDP design is that the deformability limit of the intervertebral disc cannot be defined precisely since it is a structure which retains structural integrity from liquid movement into and out of its core. Since bone fixation effects the disc stiffness, an attempt to match excised disc mechanical properties is no longer the sole criteria, rather in addition to this, the form of the disc, i.e., fibrous nature is also equally important to the motivation for use of textile composites in the concept of an artificial disc. In this regard, a more fundamental problem is that, the importance of simulating the hollow, liquid filled form, i.e., hollow nature of the IVD, is not yet fully determined. From the viewpoint of mechanical properties and processability, it does appear however that a solid, composite IVDP is most desirable.

CONCLUSIONS

The design, optimisation and compressive behaviour our concept of the IVDP have been presented in this paper. The natural IVD was replicated successfully using weft knitted textile fabrics. The rationale for use of weft knitted fabrics is the need for elastomeric or highly compliant characteristics while improving overall stiffness. It was found that the dimensions of the IVDP (polymeric core region) were vital in order for successful encapsulation with a composite layer. For the case of a hollow IVDP, it was determined that for the sake of a uniform thickness product, speed profiles in rotational moulding are critical.

From a comparison of the compressive behaviour of the IVDPs tested, it was the solid, composite IVDP that displayed the most desired mechanical properties. This is a clear indication that while the fibrous nature of the disc allows for replication of form and properties of the natural disc, the simulation of the hollow property of the natural disc, from a mechanical point of view is not essential.

REFERENCES

1. Ramakrishna S., Ramaswamy S., Teoh S.H., Hastings G.W and Tan C.T., "Application of Textiles and Textile Composites Concepts for Biomaterials Development", *Proceedings Tex Comp 3, The Third International Symposium*, Aachen, Germany, December 9-11, 1996, Session 6: Opportunities and Applications of Composites, pp.27/1-27/27.
2. Bao Q-B., McCullen M., Higham P.A., Dumbleton J.H and Yuan H.A., "The Artificial Disc: Theory, Design and Materials", *Biomaterials*, Vol. 17, No. 12, 1996, pp. 1157-1167.
3. Teoh S.H., Sin K.K., Chan L.S., and Hang C.C., "Computer Controlled Liquid Rotational Moulding of Medical Prosthesis", *Rotation*, Vol. 3, No. 3, 1994, pp 10-16.
4. Latour Jr. R.A. and Black J., "Development of FRP structural Biomaterials: Ultimate Strength of the fiber/Matrix Interfacial Bond in In-ViVo Simulated Environments," *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research*, Vol. 26, 1992, pp. 593-606.
5. Lee C.K., Langrana N.A., Parsons J.R. and Zimmerman M.C., "Development of a Prosthetic Intervertebral Disc", *Spine* Vol. 6, No. 6 supplement, 1991, pp. S253-S260.
6. Stokes IAF. "Surface Strain on Human Intervertebral Disc", *Journal of Orthopaedic Research*, Vol. 5., 1987, pp. 348-355
7. Best B.A., Guilak F., Setton L.A., Zhu W., Saed-Nejad F., Ratcliffe A., Weidenbaum M and Mow V.C., "Compressive Mechancial Properties of the Human annulus Fibrosus and Their Relationship to Biochemical Composition", *Spine*, Vol. 19, No. 2, 1994, pp. 212-221.